

**A DESIGN PROCEDURE FOR HORIZONTAL CYLINDRICAL GRP VESSELS
SUPPORTED ON TWIN SADDLES**

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ABSTRACT

Experimental results obtained from a range of horizontal cylindrical CSM reinforced polyester vessels supported on twin saddles are compared with the predictions of an isotropic material cylindrical shell analysis. In view of the good agreement the analysis is used to carry out a parameter study. On the basis of these results a procedure is proposed to obtain an estimate of the maximum strain in such vessels when full of liquid. This approach should provide a design method which avoids unduly high vessel strains in the immediate support region.

INTRODUCTION

Horizontal GRP storage vessels are currently used in a wide range of industries for storing dangerous chemicals, at either atmospheric or modest internal pressure. They are supported by either rings or saddles located a short distance from the vessel ends, or alternatively from a pair of full length beams. When saddles are used, the liquid filled tank is free to deform from the circular profile in the unsupported regions above the saddles. This results in high radial forces at the highest point of the supports, known as the saddle horn. These forces cause secondary bending stresses in the circumferential direction which are tensile on the inner surface.

The magnitude of these peak stresses is highly dependent on the saddle design, the location of the saddles relative to the vessel ends and the saddle/vessel interface conditions. In respect of the interface, some designers use a layer of rubber between the saddle and the vessel to even out any irregularities and to provide an element of radial flexibility at the horn. In other cases a layer of polypropylene is used to provide a near friction-free surface where thermal expansions are anticipated. A further alternative is to use a 'wet' GRP grouting between the vessel and support to ensure a perfect fit at the interface.

The existing Standards for GRP pipes and vessels [1,2] give only sparse information on the design of the support and do not provide a method to quantify the strains arising from the support reactions. As a result designers have tended to use the methods presented in BS 5500 [3] for metallic vessels, with a limiting strain value and a large factor of safety. It could be argued that GRP vessels and pipes are at a greater risk than their metallic counterparts since incompatible saddle design and poor fit can cause local cracking of the brittle resin rich inner surface layer. Recent experimental work by the authors [4,5] has indicated the way these inner surface cracks develop with increasing saddle loads.

It is clear therefore that a proven theoretical analysis is required to predict the maximum strains in the support region and to thereby establish a design procedure. As a first step in this direction experimental investigations were undertaken to examine the influence of certain vessel and support parameters. These results have been compared with the predictions of an analytical approach, developed by Tooth et al [6,7], which is based on an isotropic cylindrical shell analysis. On the basis of this a parameter study has been carried out and a design procedure proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

In order to provide information on the important parameters of the support problem, a number of experiments have been conducted on different diameter vessels ranging from 250 to 2000 mm. In the case of the smaller diameters (250, 400 and 500 mm) the vessels were loaded centrally in a testing machine. The larger vessels of 1000 and 2000 mm dia were fluid filled and supported on twin saddles.

Centrally Loaded Vessels

From earlier work on steel vessels it was found that if a section of an empty vessel in the support region is isolated, inverted and subject to vertical loading applied through a centrally located saddle, the resulting stresses in the support region will realistically model those of a fluid filled vessel supported on twin saddles. The loading corresponds to the saddle 'reactive' force which, for a symmetrically supported vessel, is one half of the weight of the vessel and the liquid contents.

The GRP 'vessels' or pipes used in these tests were manufactured by the hand lay-up method from CSM reinforced polyester. Three different diameters were tested, viz., 250, 400 and 500 mm with lengths approximately five times the radii and an average wall thickness of 5.5 mm with a glass content of 2.4 kg/m². The models were supported at the ends which

were maintained circular and mounted horizontally in a screw driven compression testing machine.

The loose steel saddles, which were of rigid construction, were carefully fitted to the vessel profile, using an unreinforced polyester resin between the saddle and the vessel. Three different saddle/vessel interface conditions were used for the tests employing layers of rubber, polypropylene and steel. The widths of the saddles were approximately 25, 50 and 75 mm for the 250, 400 and 500 mm dia vessels respectively. A range of saddle angles from 120 to 160° were investigated.

The vessels were extensively strain gauged on both the inner and outer surfaces. Particular attention was given to the immediate saddle horn region where previous investigations had indicated that the maximum strain occurred. Full details of these tests, which include the progressive loading of the 'vessel' to failure, are given in Ref 5. For the purpose of the present work attention is confined to the strain values in the 'elastic' range.

Twin Saddle Supported Vessels

The vessels used in these tests were of 1000 and 2000 mm dia and 4000 mm in length (tan to tan) with semi-ellipsoidal ends. They were constructed using the hand lay-up method from CSM reinforced polyester. Basic steel saddles of rigid construction were fabricated with a saddle angle of 180° and of widths of 140 and 250 mm for the 1000 and 2000 mm dia vessels respectively. The inside radius of the basic saddles was greater than the outside radius of the vessels in order to allow a range of insert plates to be bolted to the saddles. In this way the influence of a number of different widths, saddle angles and interface materials (steel, polypropylene and rubber) could be examined, using the same basic saddle. The insert plates were 6 and 12 mm thick for the 1000 and 2000 mm dia vessels respectively.

As with the smaller diameter vessels, a moulded surface of unreinforced polyester resin was produced as a seating for the test saddle and also to encapsulate the outer surface strain gauges and the associated gauge wires. This was formed using an extra wide polypropylene insert plate mounted in the saddle as a mould. Unreinforced polyester resin was poured from the saddle horns to produce a smooth continuous resin surface. In addition to this when each of the insert plates were in position they were individually grouted to the cast resin layer. This was carried out by coating the respective saddle interface plates with a filled polyester resin. The vessel was then lowered on to the saddle in the correct location and filled with water up to the saddle horn level. As the vessel was filled, the excess resin extruded out resulting in a 'perfect' fit between the saddle and vessel. The arrangement was left in this condition before testing until the resin layer was cured. Adhesion of the insert plate and vessel was prevented by the use of release agent and tape.

The vessels were extensively strain gauged on both the saddle and vessel centre profiles, with particular attention being given to the immediate horn region, on both the inner and outer surfaces. The vessels were progressively filled with water and the strain levels recorded at intervals corresponding to one tenth by weight of the full vessel. It was found that the maximum value of strain occurred in the circumferential

direction, near the horn of the saddle, when the vessel was full of water.

In the case of the 1000 mm dia vessel, the saddle width was varied from 60 to 140 mm in steps of 20 mm and the distance of the saddles from the vessel ends was varied from 150 to 1050 mm in steps of 300 mm. In the case of the 2000 mm dia vessel a saddle width of $0.2 \times$ vessel radius (200 mm) only was used throughout, since it was found, with the 1000 mm vessel, that the influence of the width was relatively small. Saddle angles of 120 to 180° in steps of 20° were investigated, for both rubber and steel interfaces, on both vessels.

On completion of the tests on the 1000 mm dia vessel, extensive destructive testing was carried out to determine the variation of the wall thickness and the glass content and to evaluate the elastic properties of the vessel material.

In the case of the 2000 mm dia vessel it was not possible to carry out destructive testing since further work is in progress. However the modulus was obtained from small specimens tested in bending, which were removed from the nozzle cut-outs. The average wall thickness value was obtained from ultrasonic tests taken in the saddle and vessel centre profiles. The values obtained from these tests were used in the analytical predictions.

Typical Experimental Results

As indicated it was found that the maximum strain occurred in the circumferential direction near the saddle horn and on the outer surface of the vessel. A typical set of results, which is representative of all diameters tested (250 to 2000 mm), is shown in Figure 1. This graph shows the variation of the circumferential strain on the outer surface, round the saddle centre profile from the nadir ($\theta = 0^\circ$) to the zenith ($\theta = 180^\circ$) for both steel (i.e rigid) and rubber interfaces. An enlarged plot of the strain in the immediate region of the saddle horn is also shown on Figure 1. The plot clearly shows the local nature of the high strains in the vessel and further that the peak values are reduced when a rubber interface is used. Further details of the results obtained on the 1000 mm dia vessel are given in Ref [8].

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

When a cylindrical vessel is supported over a relatively small contact area it is permissible to assume a simplified form for the distribution of the interface force acting between the vessel and support. However, when larger supports are used - such as saddles - the distribution of these forces is more complicated and a comprehensive treatment is required. The first such treatment was presented by Zick [9] for the metallic vessel, in 1951. Such was the insight of Zick that this approach still forms the basis of the relevant section in BS 5500 [3] which is used by most designers in the UK. The approach was semi-empirical in that beam and ring analyses were modified so that the mathematical model used for the vessel predicted stress values which agreed with the experimental results he had available.

More exact analyses, for the isotropic shell have been provided by other workers, notably Krüpká [10], who developed a semi-bending theory,

and by Tooth et al [6,7], who used the complete cylindrical shell equations. Since the CSM lay-up may be assumed to have a high degree of isotropy it is considered that this treatment is appropriate for these vessels. The approach by Tooth may be summarised as follows:-

1. The known forces - self weight, liquid fill and pressure are represented as double Fourier series, giving the radial pressure p_r , at a general point (x, θ) in the cylinder of length L ,

$$p_r = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} p_{n,m} \cos n\theta \sin m \pi x/L$$

where $p_{n,m}$ corresponds to the applied loading terms. Using the shell equations the radial displacements in the saddle region due to these forces can be found, assuming the vessel is supported at the ends in a way in which the circularity of the ends is maintained throughout.

2. The saddle support region is divided into a series of discrete but as yet unknown radial forces. These are assumed to be either uniformly distributed over the discrete areas, or line loads at the centre of the areas, which extend across the width of the saddle. The tangential forces are not considered for the loose saddle which in this case is assumed frictionless.
3. The total vessel and saddle radial displacements due to these unit saddle forces are found using an influence area method - see [6].
4. Using the radial compatibility at the saddle interface and overall equilibrium the unknown interface forces can be found.
5. These interface forces and the applied loading are then applied to the vessel to determine the stresses and strains using the cylindrical shell equations.

When the saddles are loose, as with the GRP vessel, the vessel must be allowed freedom to move inwards, i.e away from the saddle, so that contact between the saddle and vessel may be lost. This requirement is incorporated into the analysis and results in a loss of contact immediately below the horn. When a rubber interface is used its flexibility, obtained from experiments carried out on the neoprene rubber, may be incorporated into the radial compatibility equation. For this the results of the tests on the rubber were linearised for ease of calculation.

THEORETICAL COMPARISONS WITH THE EXPERIMENTS

Typical results from the experiments previously described are compared with the predictions of the theoretical analysis outlined above.

Centrally Loaded Vessels

The maximum circumferential strain values for a saddle load of 4 kN are presented in Figure 2, for the 400 and 500 mm dia vessels and for saddles of embracing angle θ ranging from 120 to 160°. In these cases experimental results for both the rubber and steel interfaces are given with the prediction for the rigid saddle analysis. In addition to the

rigorous saddle analysis the prediction of strain, assuming the interface pressure is uniformly distributed over the entire saddle interface, is also given. This latter analysis is over-optimistic and should not be used.

Twin Saddle Supported Vessels

Figures 3, 4 and 5 relate to the 1000 mm dia water filled vessel and present the maximum circumferential strains for various saddle widths, angles, locations and interface materials (steel and rubber). In each case the predictions obtained from the saddle analysis are presented with the corresponding values obtained from BS 5500 [3].

Figure 6 shows a similar plot for the maximum strains obtained from the 2000 mm dia water filled vessel. It was found in this case that the unreinforced polyester layer, which encapsulated the strain gauges and the associated wires, was thicker (5 to 7 mm) than originally intended. Although the modulus of the layer was much smaller than the GRP of the vessel (having a ratio of 1:6), it was established that in a bending mode the influence of the layer was significant. This was assessed from certain beam experiments, with and without the layer and also with the aid of simple compound beam and bar analyses. On the basis of these tests the results from the shell analysis were modified in an appropriate manner.

General Comment

The comparisons between the experimental and analytical results, given in Figures 2 to 6, show the measure of agreement for the range of vessels (400 to 2000 mm dia) investigated. At an early stage in the experimental work it was appreciated that some variations were likely to occur in the results obtained from different vessels of the same nominal geometry and specification due to the inherent variability of the material both in thickness and property from this form of construction. As a result other variations were likely when the same vessel was re-tested with the saddle horn located at a different part of the vessel. In addition, the fact that loose saddles were employed created another area of variability since non-uniform fit could well cause high peak stresses at certain points of contact.

In large measure the problem of fit was avoided by using the moulded unreinforced polyester layer. However, the material lay-up differences remain and since the peak strains occur in a region where the bending mode predominates these differences, which are associated with the local glass content at the inner and outer surfaces, are crucial. In such cases quite different peak strains could occur in vessels which are nominally geometrically similar.

In the light of the above it is considered that the agreement of the experimental results with those predicted by the cylindrical shell analysis (assuming material isotropy, constant wall thickness and neglecting deformation of the vessel ends) is remarkably good. The analysis may thus be considered acceptable to use as the basis of a parameter study of these vessels. The steel interface is used for this since the predicted values of strain are always higher in magnitude.

PARAMETER STUDY

To provide the designer with a simple method to obtain an estimate of the maximum strain in the twin saddle supported liquid filled cylindrical storage vessel a parameter study has been carried out using the analysis referred to earlier. The approach is applicable to CSM reinforced plastic vessels where isotropy is a reasonable approximation. The rigid loose saddle case has been considered since this predicts the highest values of peak strain. It corresponds to either a fabricated steel saddle or one of reinforced concrete. It was also assumed that the interface surface between the support and vessel was frictionless, that is the interface forces were entirely radial. Based on this study the following factors were identified,

- The vessel radius, r
- The vessel wall thickness, t
- The cylindrical length of the vessel (tan to tan), L
- The total saddle embracing angle, θ
- The saddle width, W
- The distance between the saddle centres, d
- The distance of the saddles from the tangent lines, A
- The weight of the contents of the dished ends, W_e
- The specific gravity of the vessel contents, γ
- The vessel material properties, E and ν .

Each of these parameters have been considered and, where possible, uncoupled from the others by considering an artificially long vessel of length L equal to $24r$. This was selected so that the vessel ends and the saddles were remote and thus the behaviour of a single saddle could be studied in isolation. The other factors were progressively introduced.

This approach is applicable to a wide range of data. The study, however, has been restricted so that the geometric and material parameters fall within the scope of GRP vessels, which are likely to be supported by saddles. As a result the maximum strain equation can be simplified. Some terms are linearised and others combined together to provide a composite factor, such as k_1 . The restraints imposed on the study are summarised below:-

1. $4 \leq L/r \leq 8$
2. $0.25 \leq A/r \leq 3$
3. $5500 \leq E \leq 9000 \text{ MN/m}^2$
4. $40 \leq r/t \leq 75$ for $r \leq 750 \text{ mm}$
 $50 \leq r/t \leq 80$ for $r > 750 \text{ mm}$
5. $500 \leq r \leq 1500 \text{ mm}$
6. $1500 \leq \epsilon_{\text{predicted}} \leq 2500 \text{ } \mu\epsilon$
7. $W = 0.2r$
8. $0.8 \leq \gamma \leq 2.0$

On this basis the following equation was obtained:-

$$\text{Maximum Strain} = \pm k_1 k_2 \frac{L}{E} \left(\frac{r}{t}\right)^2 (\gamma) \left[1 + \frac{(12-d/r)^2}{880}\right] \left[1 + \frac{2W_e}{W_c}\right] \mu\epsilon$$

where,

- k_1 = a factor varying with the r/t ratio and θ , given in Table 1.
- k_2 = a factor varying with r/t and A/r given in Figure 7
- E = Young's modulus of elasticity for the CSM composite (N/mm^2)
- L = Cylindrical length (tan to tan) (mm)
- r = Mean radius of the vessel (mm)
- t = vessel wall thickness (mm)
- γ = Specific gravity of contents
- d = Distance between the saddle centres (mm)
- A = Distance of saddles from the tangent lines (mm)
- W_e = Weight of the contents of one dished end (N)
- W_c = Weight of contents of cylindrical part of vessel (N).

It should be noted that in the above expressions the width is taken as 0.2r. It is considered that this width provides optimum support for these vessels. With regard to the use of Table 1 to obtain k_1 , it was found that results of sufficient accuracy were obtained using the nearest values of r/t and linearly interpolating for saddle angles other than those explicitly tabulated. The variation of Poisson's ratio ν in the range 0.30 to 0.34 had a negligible effect on the peak strain values and, therefore, was not included in the maximum strain equation.

The accuracy of using the above maximum strain equation together with Table 1 for k_1 and Figure 7 for k_2 has been checked by examining numerous vessels. From these, the maximum difference between the predicted peak strain from the equation and that of the actual shell analysis was found to be 14%. This difference could be reduced, but in so doing it is likely that the complexity of the procedure would be considerably increased. It is considered that at this stage the equation presented provides an acceptable design method for estimating the maximum strain values.

DESIGN APPROACH

The value of the maximum strain in the proposed vessel can be calculated using the appropriate vessel and material data available at the design stage. If the derived strain falls outwith 1500 - 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ then the result is invalid. The wall thickness should be increased or the saddle geometry changed and the calculation repeated. An acceptable value of the maximum strain is the lower of 2000 $\mu\epsilon$ or 0.1 x extension to failure of the unreinforced resin [1].

It is important that a good uniform fit is provided between the saddle and the vessel. It is also worthwhile to build into the support an element of radial flexibility to relieve the high value of the interface force at the horn. A further factor of safety is often obtained since the actual vessel wall thickness is invariably greater than that specified in the design.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

The parameter study presented in this paper has provided a simple equation to obtain an estimate of the maximum strain in fluid filled horizontal vessels supported on two saddles. The analytical work is a first step and clearly there is scope for further work to incorporate the influence of the rubber interface, the saddle flexibility, the flexibility of the ends of the vessel and the use of various reinforcing laminates. It could well be, however, that the present approach will provide an

adequate design method without these refinements, thus providing a method of assessment for these peak strains.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are indebted to the UK Polymer Engineering Group of the Science and Engineering Research Council (UK) for sponsorship, encouragement and support. Also to the associated Industrial sponsors who willingly contributed to the programme.

Table 1

The factor k_1 for various r/t ratios and saddle angles θ

θ \ r/t	40	50	60	70	80
180°	1.950	1.860	1.789	1.679	1.588
160°	2.245	2.150	1.926	1.796	1.764
140°	2.897	2.825	2.752	2.679	2.607
120°	3.589	3.579	3.568	3.506	3.456

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FIG.1 TYPICAL VARIATION OF CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAIN ROUND THE SADDLE CENTRE PROFILE FOR BOTH STEEL AND RUBBER INTERFACES - EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

FIG.3 MAXIMUM CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAINS FOR THE 1000 MM DIA WATER FILLED VESSEL, 180° SADDLE ANGLE, 750 MM FROM END FOR VARIOUS SADDLE WIDTHS - EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL RESULTS.

FIG.2 MAXIMUM CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAINS FOR THE CENTRALLY LOADED VESSELS FOR VARIOUS SADDLE ANGLES - EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL RESULTS.

FIG. 4 MAXIMUM CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAINS FOR THE 1000 MM DIA WATER FILLED VESSEL, 100 MM WIDE SADDLE, 750 MM FROM END FOR VARIOUS SADDLE ANGLES - EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL RESULTS.

FIG. 5 MAXIMUM CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAINS FOR THE 1000 MM WATER FILLED VESSEL, 100 MM WIDE SADDLE, 180° SADDLE ANGLE FOR VARIOUS SADDLE LOCATIONS - EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL RESULTS.

FIG. 6 MAXIMUM CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAINS FOR THE 2000 MM DIA WATER FILLED VESSEL, 200 MM WIDE SADDLE, 750 MM FROM END FOR VARIOUS SADDLE ANGLES - EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL RESULTS.

FIG. 7 THE FACTOR k_2 IN THE EQUATION FOR MAXIMUM STRAIN, FOR VARIOUS R/T AND A/R RATIOS.